

THE IMPORTANCE OF REGIONAL INVESTMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY

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In the current process of globalization, all countries set their main goal to become one of the most developed countries in the world by developing and stabilizing their economy and improving their macroeconomic indicators. A developed economy is inextricably linked with the stable growth of the country's macroeconomic indicators, as well as the increase of the country's all-round contribution to the world market, and positive indicators of the level of well-being of the population [1]. Therefore, the instrument that ensures the effective economic and social development of the country in a short period of time, as well as gaining its place among the world countries, as well as the improvement of the country's infrastructure and many microeconomic and macroeconomic indicators, is attracted to the country. are investments.

Today, at the stage of globalization and technological armament in the world, the role of investment flow in the interpretation of the combination of economic development is of great importance. In order to attract foreign investments through the position of the recipient state, the created investment potential in the country, the modern infrastructure, the socio-economic policy of improving the investment environment, in particular foreign they focus on the unhindered entry of companies, the inviolability of private property, the establishment of special economic and small industrial zones in the country to direct their own capital as a business entity, and the availability of tax and other financial benefits [2]. According to President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Any country that has pursued an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. That is why investment is the driver of the economy, it is no exaggeration to say that it is the heart of the economy [3]". One of the main benefits of foreign capital for the recipient countries is the improvement of the existing infrastructure and the creation of favorable conditions for the population. Therefore, the regional distribution of the investments attracted to the country is very important for the development of the country, the lifestyle and well-being of the local population.

Currently, in order to improve the annual foreign investments attracted to our country and their equal and rational distribution among the regions,

reforms are being carried out continuously, and a number of measures are being taken to increase the attractiveness of the investment environment of the regions. Local - regional, city, district hokims are given a number of tasks to study the problems of the territory assigned to them and eliminate them, to use the existing investment potential and potential of the regions effectively

As a result of the investment environment created in our country and benefits from taxes, duties and other state payments provided to attract foreign investors, most of the capital investments in our country are accounted for by foreign investments (Figure 1). In 2017, almost a quarter of the total investments were foreign investments, and by 2022, this figure will be 42.8%. 97.0 trillion in 2022 from direct foreign investments and loans to the economy of our country. Sums of investments in fixed capital were absorbed, their share in the total investments in the Republic was 36.0%, and compared to 2021, it was 104.3%

It is important that the investment environment of all regions in the country is attractive to investors at the same or similar level, because it is important to achieve economic growth through investments and to further improve the attractiveness of the investment environment in the country and its regions while increasing the share of foreign direct investment. plays a decisive role. This, in turn, shows the need to develop scientific proposals and practical recommendations for regional investment policy and its improvement in attracting foreign investments [4].

Figure 1. The share of foreign investments and loans in fixed capital investments in 2017-2022 (in %) [5]

Attracting regional investments to the country will lead to the creation of a large number of jobs for the local population, directly and indirectly, due to the emergence of enterprises operating in various fields, the expansion of the scope and size of existing enterprises due to the attracted capital. It should not be

forgotten that the attraction of regional investments means improved infrastructure, which reduces transport and production costs, increases economic and social efficiency, and allows enterprises to work more efficiently, which leads to higher productivity. Areas with good infrastructure are more attractive to both local and international investors, leading to increased capital inflows and economic development. It is worth noting that regional investment helps reduce regional disparities by promoting balanced development in different regions, creating better infrastructure and economic opportunities, ensuring that rural and underdeveloped areas also benefit from economic growth, and reducing poverty and social inequalities. helps to reduce and develop a more inclusive society. In June-July 2023 alone, 863.9 bln. investments worth soums were attracted, at the same time, 1579 new jobs were created within the framework of these projects in order to reduce the level of unemployment of the population and improve the quality of life (Table 1). As a result of the implementation of these projects, 1065 people of Tashkent region, 288 people of Fergana region, 144 people of Bukhara region, 27 people of Samarkand region, 55 people of Surkhandarya region in need of work were provided with jobs.

Table 1

Industrial projects launched in June-July 2023 as part of regional investment programs in regions [5]

Project serial number	Implemented area of project	Project value (billion soums)	Number of created jobs	Project serial number	Implemented area of project	Project value (billion soums)	Number of created jobs
1	Bukhara	1.7	4	14	Tashkent region.	130.5	100
2	Bukhara	10	70	15	Tashkent region.	25	510
3	Bukhara	68.6	70	16	Tashkent region.	21.4	40
4	Ferghana	6	30	17	Tashkent region.	5.7	15
5	Samarkand	32	7	18	Tashkent	8.8	15

					region.		
6	Samarkand	16.9	20	19	Tashkent region.	146.4	100
7	Surkhandar ya	105.7	20	20	Tashkent region.	2.3	10
8	Surkhandar ya	3	35	21	Tashkent region.	2	5
9	Tashkent region.	11.9	15	22	Tashkent region.	1	10
10	Tashkent region.	8.5	60	23	Ferghana	9.1	210
11	Tashkent region.	56.3	25	24	Ferghana	5	22
12	Tashkent region.	47.5	60	25	Ferghana	3	8
13	Tashkent region.	130.5	100	26	Ferghana	5.1	18

Our country, the Republic of Uzbekistan, is among the countries whose investment potential is increasing year by year, the investment environment is improving year by year, and the opportunities, facilities, tax and duty benefits provided to investors attract them to make active investments. Nevertheless, taking into account the incomparable benefit and progressive positive impact of foreign investments on the country's economy, the significant contribution to the wider promotion of modernization and innovation, increasing the investment attractiveness of our country, direct investment in a larger volume It is desirable to develop new effective, innovative ways of attracting foreign investments.

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